

Comparison of biodegradable polycaprolactone nanofibers and synthetic polyamide nanofibers as a novel, sustainable sorbent for a spin filter microextraction of xenobiotics from river water

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ABSTRACT

We evaluated the application of nanofibers made from different biodegradable and synthetic polymers as sorbents in a new technique of spin filter fiber-microextraction. Biodegradable polycaprolactone fibers, produced via the meltblowing process exhibited robust hydrophobic interactions with lipophilic analytes and were the most effective. The highly porous and permeable structure of the fibrous material ensured exhaustive extraction of xenobiotics from river water. Recovery rates ranged from 81.8 to 105.2 %, except for 4-nitrophenol, a more polar analyte, for which the recovery was 60 %. Only 10 s were needed for activation, extraction, and elution, significantly reducing the time required to complete the procedure in only 30 s per sample. Our method exhibited excellent analytical performance, achieving linearity in the range of 50–2000 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ for most analytes (100–2000 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ for PNP and 2-CP; and 100–1000 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ for PER) with a coefficient of determination (R^2) greater than 0.9952. The limits of detection were recalculated based on the slope of the calibration curves and the standard deviation of six replicate measurements at the lowest calibration point for each analyte, yielding values in the range of 7.0–36.6 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$. Repeatability between extractions (i.e. inter-extraction precision) was evaluated by performing six parallel runs using different cartridges ($n = 6$). The obtained RSD precision values ranged from 2.2 to 3.3 % demonstrating the excellent uniformity of the nanofibrous materials filled in the devices. We also assessed the reusability of the individual cartridges by performing six consecutive extractions on the same spin filter (i.e. intra-cartridge precision, $n = 6$), yielding RSD values between 1.1 and 3.6 %. These results confirm that the spin filters cartridges filled with polycaprolactone nanofibers can be effectively reused for multiple extractions in absence of sample carry-over effect.

1. Introduction

Chlorophenols (CPs) are organic contaminants that are defined as having at least one chlorine atom attached to a phenol ring [1], and are essential for producing agricultural pesticides, pharmaceuticals, dyes, and preservatives [2]. 2-Chlorophenol (2-CP), 2,4-dichlorophenol (2,4-DCP), 2,4,6-trichlorophenol (2,4,6-TCP), and pentachlorophenol have been identified as priority contaminants in both the United States and the European Union [2], and widespread human exposure to these compounds is associated with cardiovascular, respiratory, mental, and digestive disorders [1].

Despite the innovations in analytical instruments, the sample preparation remains essential [3], particularly when dealing with complex biological and environmental matrices, as it ensures the removal of interferences, helps to preconcentrate the trace-level analytes, and modifies the matrix to make it more compatible with the analytical instruments [4]. Since sample preparation accounts for nearly half the total analysis time and is the largest source of error, current trends in developing of new sample preparation approaches focus on simplifying and eliminating unnecessary, time-consuming steps through miniaturization and automation [5].

In recent years, several miniaturized extraction strategies have been

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developed and implemented for the extraction of CPs, these strategies include headspace solid phase microextraction [6–8], supported liquid extraction [9], online solid phase extraction [10], and spin column micro-solid phase extraction (SC- μ SPE) [11]. The latter is a relatively new, miniaturized sample preparation strategy, in which the centrifugal force propels the sample and the solvent through the sorbent, and careful selection of rotor speed is essential to ensure efficient analyte retention [12]. While such devices were initially used for sample filtration and DNA purification, they have recently gained popularity as extraction tools. As in conventional solid phase extraction (SPE), the process is exhaustive or nearly exhaustive, but it consumes much smaller amounts of sorbent and organic solvent. Although the column must be repeatedly placed in the centrifuge and manually reloaded after each step (washing, sample loading, and elution), this design reduces manipulation error while enhancing trapping capacity compared with other miniaturized methods such as pipette-tip μ -SPE [12]. Consequently, this cartridge-based approach is easy to operate, requires minimal sample and elution volumes, and eliminates the need for solvent evaporation. For example, Namera et al. were among the first to introduce a spin column featuring a thin monolithic silica disc with a 4.3 mm internal diameter and 1.5 mm thickness fixed at the bottom of the column unit for extracting amphetamines and 3,4-methylenedioxyamphetamines from urine [13]. The small bed volume and minimal sorbent amount significantly reduced the required sample size and organic solvent usage. Saito et al. reported the application of a similar monolithic silica device to extract dibucaine and naphazoline from serum [14]. Zhang et al. proposed using a polydopamine-modified monolithic spin column to extract organophosphorus pesticides from urine [15].

The choice of sorbent material strongly influences extraction efficiency, which has driven major developments in miniaturized extraction techniques toward the use of novel materials and nanomaterials [16]. Due to their large surface-to-volume ratio, superior chemical and mechanical stability, and the ability to modify their surfaces, nanofibers have emerged as interesting, novel sorbents [17]. High yield and reliable batch to batch reproducibility can be achieved when producing different polymer nanofibers by electrospinning [18,19]. The ease of manufacturing, and variety of polymers provide a large portfolio of sorbents that can be obtained at a low cost and have different levels of selectivity, hydrophobicity, and other properties [20]. Seidi et al. prepared a composite nanofibers from polyamide, graphene oxide and polypyrrole. These nanofibers were used as a sorbent in SC- μ SPE to determine parabens in milk [21]. Similarly, Nejabati et al. prepared biodegradable nanofibers by electrospinning a mixture of gelatin, soybean oil, fumed silica, silver nanoparticles, and activated carbon. These were applied as sorbents in the same microextraction technique to detect trace amounts of five petroleum pollutants in water [22]. Their results demonstrated the satisfactory extraction efficiency of the electrospun composite nanofibers as the packing material for this method. However, it is essential to explore other materials with diverse chemistries that can enhance extraction efficiency and selectivity.

To address concerns about the environmental impact of polymer-based materials used in extraction and their disposal, emphasis should be placed on using biodegradable polymers, making extraction sorbents reusable, and reducing the number of extraction steps that rely on disposable materials [23]. Polycaprolactone (PCL) and poly-3-hydroxybutyrate (PHB) are promising biodegradable polymers for preparing nanofibers [23]. Despite being biodegradable, PCL also exhibits sufficient stability, with some studies showing it remains stable for up to 3–4 years [24,25]. PCL and PHB are both polyesters with long aliphatic backbones that make them predominantly hydrophobic [24, 26]. Therefore, they can, interact well with hydrophobic analytes, such as chlorophenols and pesticides, through hydrophobic and van der Waals interactions, which aid in the preconcentration. Nectoux et al. reported that PCL was more hydrophobic than the commonly used polyamide 6 (PA6) due to its ester group and longer carbon chain, making it suitable for extracting lipophilic compounds [27]. PHB has

been suggested as a biodegradable alternative to synthetic petroleum polymers, such as polypropylene (PP) [26], and exhibits superior permeability and a smaller water contact angle than PP (86° vs. 129°) [10,26] which favors sorbent wetting and contact with analytes. Overall, biodegradable polymers offer an environmentally friendly alternative to fully synthetic materials.

This study presents for the first time comparison between biodegradable and synthetic polymers for spin filter microextraction of xenobiotics. We investigated the following biodegradable polymers, such as PCL, and PHB, as well as their composites with PP, graphene (GR), and crown ether (dibenzo-18-crown-6-ether (CR)). We also examined synthetic polymers including polyimide (PID), polybutyleneterephthalate (PBT), polyacrylonitrile (PAN), and various polyamides as well as PA6 composites that incorporated CR, and metal oxides SiO_2 , TiO_2 , and ZrO_2 .

2. Experimental

2.1. Reagents and chemicals

The following analytical standards 2-chlorophenol (2-CP, >97 %), 2,5-dichlorophenol (2,5-DCP, >98 %), 2,3,4,6-tetrachlorophenol (2,3,4,6-TCP), Fenoxycarb (FXC, 99.5 %) and Permethrin (PER) were purchased from Fluka (Seelze, Germany). Bisphenol A (BPA, >99 %), 2,4,6-trichlorophenol (2,4,6-TCP, 98 %), 4-chlorophenol (4-CP, >99 %) were obtained from Sigma-Aldrich (Prague, Czech Republic) and p-nitrophenol (PNP) from Chemapol (Czech Republic). Dibenzo-18-crown-6-ether (purity >98 %) was purchased from Merck (Prague, Czech Republic). The acetonitrile and methanol in LC/MS purity grade >99.9 % used for material conditioning, analyte dissolution and elution, and the chromatographic mobile phase were supplied by Biosolve (Dieuze, France). Phosphoric acid (85 %) was purchased from Lachema (Czech Republic). Ultra-pure water was prepared using a Millipore Milli-Q Direct Water Purification System from Merck (Darmstadt, Germany). The conductivity of the ultrapure water was $0.055 \mu\text{S cm}^{-1}$ at 25°C ($18.2 \text{ M}\Omega\cdot\text{cm}$).

2.2. Preparation of standards and samples

Stock solutions of all 9 analytes were prepared at a concentration of 2 mg mL⁻¹ in acetonitrile and stored at 4°C . The mixed standard solution for method validation was prepared at a concentration of 50 mg l⁻¹ and stored at 4°C . The mixed standard solution for extraction optimization was prepared at a concentration of 2 mg l⁻¹ in 10 % aqueous acetonitrile. Acetonitrile was added to improve the solubility of the hydrophobic analytes. A relatively high concentration was selected to ensure strong UV responses, allowing reliable comparison of extraction performance between different nanofibers during method development. The chemical structures and characteristics of all analytes are shown in the Supplementary Material (Table S-1).

Real water samples were collected from the Elbe River in November 2024. Samples were stored in pre-cleaned glass bottles at 4°C until analysis. Six parallel extractions were performed for each nanofiber material to minimize random error and ensure repeatability. Extractions were evaluated at a concentration of 2 mg L⁻¹ in 10 % aqueous acetonitrile. Percentage recovery was determined by comparing the peak areas of extracted analytes with those obtained from the reference standard solution.

2.2. Instrumentation and software

Chromatographic analysis was performed using a Prominence LC-20AD HPLC-DAD system (Shimadzu Corporation, Japan), which was equipped with an SPD-M20A Prominence UV/VIS DAD detector, a CBM-20A communication module, two LC-20AD high-pressure pumps, a DGU-20A5 degasser unit, a SIL-20AC autosampler, and a CTO-20AC

column oven. Data evaluation and peak area integration were performed using Lab Solution software (Shimadzu Corporation, Japan). Extraction experiments were performed using MIKRO 220R centrifuge (Hettich, Germany).

2.3. Chromatographic analysis

An Ascentis Express AQ-C18 analytical column (150×4.6 mm, 2.7 μm particle size) from Supelco (Sigma-Aldrich) was used to separate the model analytes in the gradient mode at a column oven temperature of 30 °C. Acetonitrile, part A, and 0.1 % aqueous phosphoric acid, part B, were used as the components of the mobile phase. The following gradient was used for the separations: 0–2 min 35 % A in B, 2–7 min 35 % - 100 % A, 7–9 min 100 % A, 9–9.5 min 100 % - 35 % A, 9.5–11 min 35 % A. The flow rate was 1.25 mL min⁻¹ and the injection volume was 10 μL. All analytes were monitored at a detection wavelength of 210 nm.

2.4. Nanofibrous materials

We assessed nanofibers made from the following polymers: biodegradable PCL and PHB, as well as composites made from these polymers and PP, GR, and CR. We also examined synthetic polymer fibers, including PID, PBT, PAN, and various polyamides (PA4, PA6, PA6/10, PA4/6, and PA11), as well as PA6 composites that incorporated GR, CR, SiO₂, TiO₂, and ZrO₂. Mats of these fibers were prepared at different layer thicknesses using meltblowing (MB) and alternating current (AC) electrospinning. The fibrous sorbents were obtained from the Technical University Liberec. A detailed description and characterization of the nanofibrous materials, and their production can be found in the Supplementary material section (Nanofibers fabrication (Table S-2–4 and Figure S-1 and S-2 (A-C)). Detailed structures of nanofibrous disc for spin filter extraction and SEM images of the nanofibrous materials from PCL and PA6 used for the final validation and extraction are demonstrated in Fig. 1.

2.5. Extraction protocol

Discs with a diameter of 7.28 mm (microscopic detail in Fig. 1) were punched from the nanofiber mats using a stainless-steel circular press and placed into centrifugal plastic spin filters fitted inside a 2 mL Eppendorf tubes for phase collection (Fig. 2). The disc diameter was chosen to match the tube bottom to ensure proper fit in spin filter. The

extraction process consisted of the following steps: (i) Washing and activation with 200 μL methanol pipetted onto the disc, (ii) loading 600 μL of sample, and (iii) elution with 200 μL methanol. Each step was followed by centrifugation at 4000 rpm for 10 s. Washing and sample loading were done in one Eppendorf tube, and a new tube was used to collect the extract. A 10 μL of the extract was injected into the HPLC system for analysis.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Selection of polymer nanofibers

The model analytes were selected to cover a wide range of polarities, as indicated by log P values ranging from 1.9 to 6.5. Their retention was examined on nanofiber discs prepared by MB or AC electrospinning from a variety of polymers, including PCL (single and double discs), PA homopolymers and copolymers with different carbon chain lengths (PA11, PA6/10, PA4/6, PA6, and PA4), combination of PA6 and PCL, PHB, PID, PAN, PBT. Composites of PHB and PP at different weight ratios (100:0; 90:10; 80:20; 70:30; 60:40; 50:50), PA6 with addition of TiO₂ (0.05, 0.1, 0.15, and 50 %), SiO₂ (50 %), and ZrO₂ (50 %), PA6 and PCL with CR at different ratios (1:0.5; 1:1; 1:1.5), PCL with GR were also examined. In total, we tested over 30 different materials. To provide an overview of the results, a heatmap showing recovery for all fibers and analytes is presented in Fig. 3, with materials grouped into biodegradable polymers, PHB:PP and PA6+PCL blends, synthetic polymers, and additive-modified fibers. The full graphical dataset for all nanofibers is available in the Supplementary materials (Figures S-3, S-4).

Across all tested fibers, recovery generally increased with analyte lipophilicity, indicating that hydrophobic interactions were the dominant factor. Among the biodegradable materials, PCL showed the highest recoveries for all analytes, reflecting its pronounced hydrophobicity. In contrast, PHB exhibited high recovery only for PER, with poor retention of the remaining analytes. PHB, a biodegradable alternative to synthetic polymers such as PP [26], was further tested in blend fibers PHB:PP with varying PP content (Supplementary materials, Figure S-3. The highest recovery was achieved with pure PHB, whose higher permeability and lower water contact angle (86° vs. 129° for PP) [10,26] ensured better wettability and facilitated interaction with aqueous samples. However, only PER was fully recovered, FXC reached around 80 %, and the remaining analytes were poorly extracted.

Comparison of synthetic polymers revealed that PA6 fibers produced

Fig. 1. Structures of PCL and PA6 nanofibrous disc for spin filter extraction and their SEM images.

Fig. 2. Filling the spin filter with a nano-disc (left) and an Eppendorf tube with a filled spin filter (right).

Fig. 3. Heatmap of analyte recovery (%) on nanofiber sorbents, grouped by polymer type and modifications. Rows correspond to individual nanofibers, divided into biodegradable polymers, blends, synthetic polymers, and additive-modified fibers. Columns correspond to nine analytes. Color scale indicates recovery, with red = high and blue = low.

via MB exhibited the best overall performance. Polymers with longer carbon chains, such as PA6/10 AC and PA11 AC, showed higher retention of less polar analytes due to stronger hydrophobic interactions and outperformed less hydrophobic polyamides, including PA6 AC, PA6/6 AC, PA4 AC, and PA4/6 AC. In general, analyte recovery increased with lipophilicity, with polar compounds such as PNP, 2-CP, and 4-CP being retained less efficiently. PID was the next best-performing polymer, achieving only ~60% recovery for most analytes, while PAN, and PBT showed high recovery solely for PER and poor extraction for the remaining analytes.

Fibers modified with CR, GR, SiO₂, TiO₂, or ZrO₂ were also evaluated (Figure S-3,S-4 in Supplementary Material). The addition of CR was expected to enhance retention of more polar analytes through specific interactions with the ether oxygens. However, the results showed instead improved extraction of less polar compounds. This can be explained by changes in surface chemistry and morphology: incorporation of crown ether likely increased the exposure of hydrophobic moieties and raised the surface roughness, resulting in higher contact angles with increasing CR content (Figure S-2 C). Consequently, the fibers became more hydrophobic overall, which favored retention of less polar analytes. Despite the increased porosity and surface area, the addition of graphene reduced analyte recovery compared with pure PCL (Supplementary materials, Table S-4, Figure S-4). At low loading (PCL:GR 10:1) the performance was comparable to pure PCL, but at higher loading (PCL:GR 10:5) the recovery decreased. This is likely due to changes in sorbent physical properties: GR-loaded mats were somewhat adhesive and more difficult to cut and handle, which may have led to imperfect disc geometry and inconsistent seating in the spin filter. In addition, the increased contact angle reduced the wetting of the fibrous discs by the aqueous sample, which likely limited analyte-sorbent interactions. Together, these handling challenges and altered wetting behavior likely explain the lower recoveries. Similarly, incorporation of metal oxides into PA6 nanofibers produced no significant differences in analyte retention for SiO₂, TiO₂, and ZrO₂ at 50 % loading, while lower TiO₂ loadings (0.05–0.15 %) resulted in decreased retention. This effect is most likely linked to the increased adhesiveness of the material, which complicates handling in the spin filters.

Among all materials, the best recoveries were obtained with 3 mm thick fiber mats produced using the MB technique from PA 6 (97–105 %, except for 2,3,4,6-TCP 46 %), PCL (76–105 %, except for PER 35 %), two PCL discs (6 mm) (92–106 %, except for PER 48 %), and combination of PA6 and PCL (6 mm) (94–104 %, except for 2,3,4,6-TCP 65 %) (Figure S-3). The enhanced performance of these fibers is attributable to their larger surface area, increased permeability, and more flexible, fluffy structure, which improves contact with aqueous samples. These results

indicate that strong hydrophobic interactions combined with adequate wettability are critical for efficient extraction, with PA6 and PCL fibers outperforming the other tested polymers. Although PA6 and PCL fibers both outperformed the other tested polymers in terms of recovery, PCL was selected as the optimal sorbent because, in addition to its high extraction efficiency, it offers the advantage of biodegradability, thereby reducing environmental impact. Thus, PCL was retained as the primary sorbent in subsequent experiments, while PA6 was included mainly for comparative purposes. Notably, differences in analyte recovery were also observed between PA6 and PCL fibers prepared by MB and AC, and this effect is discussed in detail in the following section.

3.2. Comparison of PA6 and PCL fibers prepared by alternating current electrospinning and meltblowing

AC electrospinning uses an alternating electric field to produce fine fibers from a polymer solution, which provides reliable control over fiber diameter and alignment [28]. MB forms polymer nanofibers by pushing molten polymer through fine nozzles and stretching the fibers with high-velocity hot air, thus creating a nonwoven fiber mat [29,30]. The key difference is that AC electrospinning works with polymer solutions at room temperature, whereas MB processes molten polymer at high temperatures. While MB technology eliminates the need for organic solvents, it requires high temperatures and considerable energy input, which should be taken into account when assessing its environmental impact. In contrast, AC electrospinning operates at ambient conditions but relies on solvents, highlighting a trade-off between solvent use and energy consumption in these two fiber production methods. Although meltblown fibers are typically 1–10 μm in diameter compared to thinner fibers produced by AC electrospinning, their advantage is the robustness and airy, cotton-like structure of the mats with excellent permeability. Therefore, these materials can demonstrate different contact angle values (wettability) for the same polymers affecting the interaction of analyte with the fiber surface. We compared analyte recoveries after extraction on 2 mm thick disc sorbents made of PA6 and PCL, which were prepared by both AC electrospinning and meltblowing techniques (Fig. 4). Following activation, the MB sorbents were visibly wet during the extraction process, allowing samples to pass through quickly even before the centrifugation. In contrast, AC electrospun materials did not allow samples to pass through until centrifugation was initiated. MB materials have a fluffier structure compared to the denser, more compact AC materials. There was a clear difference in analyte recovery between PA6 prepared by AC electrospinning and MB (Fig. 4). MB PA6 performed better with more polar analytes PNP, 2-CP, and 4-CP, while AC electrospun PA6 worked better for less polar analytes 2,3,4,6-CP and

PER. The differences between AC electrospun and MB PCL fibers were less significant. A similar trend was observed for PCL as for PA6. MB PCL performed better with the more polar analytes, while AC electrospun PCL extracted less polar analytes, more effectively, particularly PER. These results suggest that more polar analytes are retained more effectively by MB materials due to their fluffier structure and higher wettability. These materials absorb moisture more easily, and the fluffier structure increases their permeability. This allows polar compounds to interact more effectively with the fiber network, improving retention. In contrast, less polar analytes may not be retained as effectively on MB fibers because the sample passes through the structure too quickly, which limits interaction time. On the other hand, AC electrospun materials may have a lower capacity to retain more polar analytes due to their denser structure and lower wettability. However, the stronger interactions between the nanofibers and less polar analytes, combined with a slower extraction process, lead to higher recovery rates for less polar compounds.

Fig. 4 also shows that PCL fibers produced by AC electrospinning performed better than the PA6 counterparts likely due to the higher hydrophobicity [27] facilitating retention of less polar analytes. MB PA6 was better suited for more polar analytes, most likely due to lower hydrophobicity and better permeability, while MB PCL performed better for less polar analytes, benefiting from stronger hydrophobic interactions. Across all evaluated combinations, MB-prepared fibers were easier to handle in the spin filter format, exhibited superior wettability, and achieved more consistent recoveries across both polar and nonpolar analytes. Based on these objective criteria, MB PA6 and MB PCL were selected as the most promising sorbents for further study.

3.3. Optimization of extraction parameters

Detailed optimization of key extraction parameters (centrifugation conditions, activation volume, desorption solvent and volume) was conducted using PCL MB as the representative sorbent, since comparable trends were expected for both polymers. PA6 MB was nevertheless included in the solvent comparison, where polymer-specific differences were anticipated (Fig. 5). All optimization conditions were tested in six independent extractions ($n = 6$). All nine analytes were included, but only representative compounds covering a broad polarity range are shown in Fig. 5, which presents the mean values with error bars representing the relative standard deviation (RSD).

Sorbent activation is important because it removes potential contaminants left in the fibers after fabrication and ensures the wetting of the fibers necessary for optimal analyte retention. We compared analyte recoveries using 3 mm thick MB PCL discs obtained after no activation

Fig. 4. Analyte recovery after extraction on PA6 and PCL nanofibrous sorbents prepared by alternating current electrospinning (AC) and meltblowing (MB).

Fig. 5. Effect of activation solvent volume (A), centrifugation time (B), centrifugation speed (C), elution solvent (D), and elution solvent volume (E) on percent analyte recovery from PCL discs (except D, which was tested on both PA6 and PCL discs). All nine analytes were included in the optimization; only representative compounds covering a broad polarity range are shown for clarity. Each condition was tested in six replicates ($n = 6$). Error bars indicate relative standard deviation (RSD,%).

with those obtained after activation using up to 800 μL methanol (Fig. 5A). Discs activated with 200 μL methanol showed 20–40 % higher recoveries than non-activated discs, while increasing the activation volume beyond 200 μL did not provide further improvement. Therefore, 200 μL was selected as the activation volume.

The choice of sample volume was based on practical considerations. After placing a spin filter into a 2 mL Eppendorf tube, the free volume was reduced to around 1 mL. Therefore, we used 200 μL methanol for activation and a sample volume of 600 μL . This configuration ensures that the total volume fits within the single Eppendorf tube, eliminating the need to discard waste or change tubes.

In spin filter extraction, the centrifugal power controls the speed at which the sample flows through the sorbent. This is important because it directly affects the analyte retention efficiency [12]. If the flow rate is too fast, the analytes may not have enough time to interact adequately with the sorbent, resulting in insufficient retention and smaller recovery. In contrast, if the flow rate is too slow, the extraction process is extended without significantly improving the performance. We tested the effects of centrifuge speeds ranging from 500 to 4000 rpm (30–1800 g), and centrifugation times from 10 to 120 s on analyte recovery for extraction on PCL discs (Fig. 5B, 5C). Slower centrifuge speeds improved recovery for PNP, with single-factor ANOVA indicating a significant effect of centrifugation speed ($p = 0.02$). However, no differences were observed for more hydrophobic analytes (single-factor ANOVA, $p > 0.3$), suggesting that retention is efficient even at short contact times, likely due to strong hydrophobic interactions between the PCL and the analytes. Recovery did not significantly change with centrifugation time (single-factor ANOVA, $p > 0.2$), indicating that analyte capture occurs rapidly. Because the sample passes through the PCL disc within 10 s,

longer centrifugation times do not further increase recovery. The consistently high recovery shows that analytes are effectively retained by the sorbent even during this short contact period. Although PNP recovery was higher at lower speeds, 10 s at 4000 rpm (1800 g) was sufficient for the entire sample to pass through the sorbent, greatly reducing the extraction time per sample. Therefore, 4000 rpm for 10 s was selected as the optimal centrifugation speed to balance analyte recovery with throughput.

The elution solvent should effectively elute all the retained analytes without their excessive dilution or loss, and should be suitable for direct injection into HPLC. We compared the effects of acetonitrile and methanol as elution solvents on analyte recovery after extraction from PA6 and PCL discs (Fig. 5D). While PCL was selected as the optimal sorbent, PA6 is included in the comparison to highlight how polymer type influences solvent performance. Despite similar elution strengths of both solvents, significant differences in analyte recovery were observed, particularly for PA6. This is likely due to the PA6 swelling in acetonitrile, as reported elsewhere. This phenomenon was observed especially for DC spun PA6 nanofibers under the high pressure in LC systems [28]. Recoveries on the PCL sorbent were not significantly affected by either of the solvent. Although PCL dissolves in acetonitrile at elevated temperatures [23], the short contact time at room temperature did not impact the recovery. Nevertheless, methanol provided superior results and was selected as the optimal elution solvent. The elution volume significantly impacts extraction and achieving a high enrichment factor. Using a smaller elution volume results in higher preconcentration of the analytes. However, if the elution volume is too small, it may not be sufficient to fully desorb and recover all the analytes from the sorbent. Therefore, it is important to find a balance that maximizes

preconcentration while ensuring a complete analyte recovery. We tested different volumes of methanol, ranging from 50 to 600 μL , for the analyte elution. We calculated the preconcentration factors by comparing the peak areas of the analytes in standard solution with a concentration of 2 mg l^{-1} to the peak areas obtained after extraction with PCL discs using different elution volumes. We then calculated the recoveries by comparing the expected preconcentration to the actual preconcentration achieved. Although elution with 600 μL of methanol yielded nearly 100 % recovery for all analytes, such a large volume reduces the achievable preconcentration factor. In contrast, reducing the elution volume to 200 μL still allowed elution of all analytes with high recoveries (79–94 %) while increasing the preconcentration factor to 2.4–2.8 (Fig. 5E). Further decreasing the elution volume led to reduced recoveries, particularly for more hydrophobic analytes, indicating that these compounds are more strongly retained by the hydrophobic sorbent and require a larger volume for efficient desorption. Based on these results, 200 μL was selected as the elution volume, representing a compromise between high preconcentration and acceptable recovery.

3.4. Effect of disc thickness on analyte recovery

We compared analyte recovery after extraction on meltblown PCL discs of various thicknesses 1, 2, 2.5, and 3 mm. These discs were punched from mats obtained directly by fabrication while 6 mm unit was obtained by placing two 3 mm discs on the top of each other in a spin filter. The results for the selected analytes are shown in Fig. 6. The more polar analytes PNP and 4-CP, with log P values of 1.9 and 2.4, respectively, exhibited significantly higher recovery in the thicker 3- and 6-mm sorbent layers compared to their thinner counterparts (Fig. 6). In contrast, less polar analytes, such as BPA, 2,5-DCP, and FXC, with log P values of 3.3, 3.1, and 4.3, respectively, exhibited sufficient extraction recovery even when using thinner discs. Similar results were obtained for discs that were 2, 2.5, 3, and 6-mm thick (Fig. 6). This difference is due to the predominantly hydrophobic nature of PCL, which stems from its aliphatic backbone [24]. More lipophilic analytes strongly interact with PCL through hydrophobic interactions, leading to a high retention even in thin disc layers. In contrast, more polar analytes are less strongly retained on PCL discs. Using thicker discs increased the contact time between the analytes and the sorbent. Therefore, the analytes were better retained. The increased recovery of more polar analytes in thicker discs also confirms that they have a higher retention capacity for these compounds without significantly increasing retention strength. Therefore, disc thickness plays an important role in the recovery of more polar analytes, such as PNP, 2-CP, and 4-CP on hydrophobic sorbents. The effect of disc thickness on analyte recovery was

evaluated by single-factor ANOVA. Six replicate extractions were performed for each thickness, and RSD values are shown as error bars in Fig. 6. For polar analytes (PNP, 4-CP), recovery was highly dependent on disc thickness, with extremely small p-values ($p = 4.46 \times 10^{-17}$ and 3.79×10^{-20}), indicating a strong effect. For less polar analytes, recoveries also increased with thickness, but the effect was less pronounced (FXC $p = 0.0012$). These results confirm that thicker discs improve retention for all analytes justifying the selection of 6 mm discs (two 3 mm layers) as optimal.

3.5. Analytical performance

The final validation parameters for the HPLC method, which covers the spin filter extraction on double PCL discs are presented in Table 1 and for combination of PA6+PCL nanofiber discs in Table 2. Neat PCL was evaluated as the primary sorbent for the method validation, while PCL+PA6 was included mainly for comparative purposes and to show the possible combination of both sorbents in one spin filter. The results of the HPLC system suitability test are reported in Supplementary material Table S-5. Linearity was measured in the range of 50–2000 $\mu\text{g l}^{-1}$ for most analytes, except for PNP and 2-CP 100–2000 $\mu\text{g l}^{-1}$; and 100–1000 $\mu\text{g l}^{-1}$ for PER. The coefficients of determination (R^2) were greater than 0.9952 for PCL, and 0.9925 for PA6+PCL. The limits of detection (LOD) and quantification (LOQ) were calculated from the calibration curve slopes using the formulas $\text{LOD} = 3.3 \times \text{SD} / \text{slope}$ and $\text{LOQ} = 10 \times \text{SD} / \text{slope}$, where SD is the standard deviation of six replicate measurements at the lowest calibration point for each analyte. The LODs were 7.0–36.6 $\mu\text{g l}^{-1}$ for PCL, and 8.1–69.1 $\mu\text{g l}^{-1}$ for PA6+PCL. The repeatability of the spin filters (inter-cartridge precision) was evaluated by extractions using six different spin filters in parallel ($n = 6$). The obtained inter-cartridge precision values ranged from 2.2 to 3.3 % RSD for PCL, and from 1.1 to 3.6 % RSD for PA6+PCL, demonstrating the excellent uniformity of the nanofibrous materials. Additionally, the intra-cartridge precision or the reusability was assessed by performing six consecutive extractions on the same spin filter ($n = 6$), yielding RSD values between 1.1 and 3.6 % for PCL, and between 0.9 and 3.8 % for PA6+PCL. This confirms that the spin filter can be effectively reused for multiple extractions. We investigated the applicability of the method by extracting model analytes spiked in surface water from the Elbe River. All analytes were extracted using doubled PCL discs, yielding high recovery rates ranging from 81.1 to 105.2 %, except for PNP, which was not retained as strongly on the PCL sorbent as more hydrophobic analytes. Recovery rates using PA6+PCL ranged from 90.3 to 104.7 %, except for 2,3,4,6-TCP, which was not fully eluted from the hydrophobic sorbent. Using 200 μL methanol for elution led to an analyte

Fig. 6. Effect of various PCL disc thickness on analyte recoveries.

Table 1

Validation parameters for the HPLC method covering the spin filter extraction using two 3 mm thick PCL discs.

	LOD [$\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$]	LOQ [$\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$]	Calibration plot $y = ax + b$	Determination coefficient ^a [R^2]	Recovery ^b [%]	Intra-cartridge precision, RSD ^c [%]	Inter-cartridge precision, RSD ^d [%]	Preconc. factor ^e
PNP	27.8	84.3	$Y = 18.333x + 1638.3$	0.9958	60.0	3.5	3.2	1.9
2-CP	17.0	51.4	$Y = 72.552x - 764.83$	0.9995	96.7	1.6	2.3	2.7
4-CP	14.9	45.3	$Y = 50.857x - 696.6$	0.9995	100.7	1.3	2.5	2.7
BPA	15.5	47.0	$Y = 99.614x - 64.71$	0.9999	101.4	2.1	2.8	2.6
2,5-DCP	9.0	27.1	$Y = 122.81x - 821.14$	0.9999	101.6	2.1	2.3	2.5
2,4,6-TCP	8.7	26.3	$Y = 115.04x + 4650.8$	0.9988	90.1	1.1	2.2	2.2
FXC	13.4	40.5	$Y = 70.106x - 693.77$	0.9995	105.2	2.4	3.3	2.5
2,3,4,6-TCP	7.0	21.3	$Y = 117.57x + 4745.8$	0.9973	81.1	1.9	2.2	2.0
PER	36.6	111.0	$Y = 68.09x - 2694.5$	0.9952	85.8	3.6	2.8	2.2

^a Linearity range: 50 – 2000 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$; PNP, 2-CP 100 – 2000 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$; PER 100 ppb – 1000 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$.^b Recovery at a concentration 2 mg L^{-1} , (direct injection of standard compared with spiked river after extraction, elution volume 600 μL).^c n = 6, 6 extraction rounds on same spin filter.^d n = 6, extraction on 6 spin filters in parallel.^e Direct injection of standard compared to sample after extraction (elution volume 200 μL).**Table 2**

Validation parameters for the HPLC method covering the spin filter extraction on combined PA6+PCL spin filters.

	LOD [$\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$]	LOQ [$\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$]	Calibration plot $y = ax + b$	Determination coefficient ^a [R^2]	Recovery ^b [%]	Intra-cartridge precision, RSD ^c [%]	Inter-cartridge precision, RSD ^d [%]	Preconc. factor ^e
PNP	31.3	94.9	$Y = 26.572x + 710$	0.9994	93.8	3.8	1.7	2.4
2-CP	8.8	26.6	$Y = 65.982x - 198.74$	0.9999	100.0	1.3	2.6	2.5
4-CP	8.1	24.5	$Y = 45.327x - 269.59$	0.9998	100.2	1.8	1.6	2.5
BPA	12.3	37.2	$Y = 91.289x - 213.37$	0.9998	101.8	1.0	1.1	2.4
2,5-DCP	9.7	29.3	$Y = 106.96x - 796.77$	0.9999	101.7	0.9	1.8	2.3
2,4,6-TCP	16.1	48.9	$Y = 81.533x + 635.88$	0.9999	93.1	2.4	3.6	1.7
FXC	10.9	33.1	$Y = 74.057x - 821.24$	0.9999	104.7	1.0	1.6	2.7
2,3,4,6-TCP	69.1	209.4	$Y = 64.726x + 6932.9$	0.9940	67.8	3.2	2.4	1.5
PER	18.9	57.2	$Y = 70.959x - 104.72$	0.9925	90.3	2.4	3.5	2.6

^a Linearity range: 50 – 2000 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$; PNP 100 – 2000 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$; 2,3,4,6-TCP 250 – 2000 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$; PER 100 – 1000 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$.^b Recovery at a concentration 2 mg L^{-1} , (direct injection of standard compared with spiked river after extraction, elution volume 600 μL).^c n = 6, 6 extraction rounds on same spin column.^d n = 6, extraction on 6 spin columns in parallel.^e Direct injection of standard compared to sample after extraction (elution volume 200 μL).

preconcentration of 1.9–2.7 on doubled PCL discs, and 1.5–2.6 on PA6+PCL discs. The comparison of both extractions is demonstrated in Fig. 7. No peaks were detected in the blank river water samples (Fig. 7., gray line), indicating that the analyte concentrations were below the current method's detection limit; using a more sensitive detection technique, such as LC-MS/MS, could improve trace-level quantification in real samples.

3.6. Comparison with other extraction methods

Table 3 compares our spin filter extraction method with similar techniques reported elsewhere [9,11,21,22]. Our method stands out due to its reduced number of steps and shorter extraction time. Competing spin filter approaches require sample loading and elution, as well as multiple centrifugation cycles necessary to improve analyte recovery. In contrast, our method requires only one centrifugation cycle for both sample loading and elution, while achieving excellent analyte recovery and repeatability comparable to or better than that of other methods. All analytes were efficiently recovered, although the more polar compound PNP showed slightly lower recovery (60 %), likely due to its reduced retention on the hydrophobic PCL fiber. The total extraction time is approximately 30 s excluding the handling time required for placing and removing samples from the centrifuge and for pipetting. Our

centrifugation cycle lasts only 10 s for activation, sample loading, and elution. This short contact time is sufficient due to the high analyte retention capacity and excellent permeability of the sorbent. Other spin filter methods require numerous centrifugation cycles for sample loading and elution, which significantly extends the overall procedure, particularly when considering the repeated sample handling.

4. Conclusion

A novel and simple method for determining of xenobiotics in river water using biodegradable PCL or synthetic PA6 nanofiber discs has been demonstrated. These fibers, which act as a sorbent, can be easily prepared using the meltblowing technique. This technique minimizes the need for the organic solvents, which are typically required in the alternating current electrospinning process. Meltblowing also allows the nanofibrous mats to be produced directly from the polymer melt in one step, enhancing both process efficiency and sustainability. These mats have a fluffy structure that provides high permeability to water compared to electrospun counterparts. The discs can then be easily cut to the desired size and placed in the spin filter cartridge that can be reused for multiple extractions with reliable repeatability. Using our spin filter extraction method, up to 48 samples can be processed simultaneously in a single run, depending on the centrifuge

Fig. 7. Chromatograms showing the separations of analytes in 2 mgL^{-1} spiked river water obtained after the direct injection (black line) and after the spin filter preconcentration and cleanup using doubled PCL nanofibrous discs (blue line) in upper part, and PA6+PCL (orange line), and blank River (violet bottom line).

Table 3

Comparison of proposed methods with others reported in the literature.

Analytes	Extraction/Analysis Method	Extraction Sorbent	Sorbent amount [mg]	Extraction/Analysis time [min]	Steps	Recovery [%]	RSD [%]	Ref.
Toluene, n-octane, p- xylene, o- xylene, and aniline	SC- μ -SPE/GC-FID	GLA-SO-FS-Ag NPs- AC nanofibers	–	23.5/12	6	94.2–102.6	<7.4	[22]
Me-P; Et-P; Pr-P	SC- μ -SPE/HPLC-UV	PA-GO-PP nanofibers	20	21/12	21	81.7–97.8	<8.6	[21]
4-CP; 2,3-DCP; 2,4-DCP; 2,4,6-TCP	SC- μ -SPE/GC-MS	MFU-4l	30	-/30	18	88.2–105.4	4.4–7.8	[11]
PNP; 2-CP; 4-CP; BPA; 2,5-DCP; 2,4,6-TCP; FXC; 2,3,4,6-TCP; PER	Stirred supported liquid disc/ HPLC-DAD	PAN nanofibers with 50 μL octanol	7–10	90/11	3	0–121.4	<13	[9]
PNP; 2-CP; 4-CP; BPA; 2,5-DCP; 2,4,6-TCP; FXC; 2,3,4,6-TCP; PER	SC- μ -SPE /HPLC-DAD	PCL nanofibers	50	0.5/11	3	60.0–105.2	<3.6	This work

2,3,4,6-TCP – 2,3,4,6-tetrachlorophenol; 2,3-DCP – 2,3-dichlorophenol; 2,4,6-TCP – 2,4,6-trichlorophenol; 2,4-DCP – 2,4-dichlorophenol; 2,5-DCP – 2,5-dichlorophenol; 2-CP – 2-chlorophenol; 4-CP – 4-chlorophenol; BPA – bisphenol A; Et-P – ethyl paraben; FXC – fenoxycarb; GLA-SO-FS-Ag NPs-AC - gelatin/soybean oil/fumed silica/Ag nano particles/activated carbon; Me-P – methyl paraben; MFU-4l - metal-organic framework synthesized from ZnCl_2 and 1H-1,2,3-triazolo[4,5-b] [4',5'-i] dibenzo[1,4]dioxin; PA6+PCL – polyamide 6 + polycaprolactone; PA-GO-PP- polyamide-graphene oxide-polypyrrole; PAN – polyacrylonitrile; PER – permethrin; PNP – para-nitrophenol; Pr-P – propyl paraben; SC- μ -SPE – Spin column micro solid phase extraction.

configuration. The highly porous and permeable structure of PCL fiber mats enables the exhaustive extraction of lipophilic analytes from river water in a very short contact time. This results in high recovery due to strong hydrophobic interactions. PCL also offers an environmentally friendly alternative to synthetic fibers because it produces similar or better recovery than other evaluated polymers. Our extractions using the spin filter cartridges in spin filters featured excellent repeatability and the devices could be reused for multiple extractions. Although we demonstrated our approach using fibers to extract and determine xenobiotics in river water, the same extraction method can be adapted to determine various other contaminants in water and other matrices.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Ewelina Czyz: Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Karolína Macháčková:** Validation, Methodology. **Jakub**

Erben: Visualization, Resources, Project administration, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Pavel Holec:** Visualization, Methodology, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **František Švec:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision. **Dalibor Šatínský:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Supplementary materials

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Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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